

SUPERVISORS' OPINIONS ON THE CHANGING REGULATIONS AND THEIR ATTITUDES TOWARDS CHANGE

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Abstract:

The job of an effective school supervisor has multiple faces. They are supposed to be mentors, strategists and managers as well as the representatives of the up-to-date regulations. Top-down changes or mandated changes originate at government or bureaucratic level. Bottom-up changes are the ones initiated by opponents of an organization. It is known that bottom-up changes take more time than top-down changes. When it comes to educational systems, it will not be wrong to say that most changes are still mandated or top-down way. This research aims to find out the supervisors' reactions towards change and see whether the heads of the department apply the procedure of change management. Qualitative data collection techniques were used to implement this study. Semi-structured interview form was used to collect data, and seven questions were posed to 9/11 participants. Obtained responses were analysed via descriptive analysis methods. Findings show that Lewin's (1947) change model theory is disregarded among MoNE authorities.

Keywords: supervisor, change management, mandated change, Lewin's change model

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1. Introduction

The job of an effective school supervisor has multiple faces. As an educational leader, supervisors are believed to have a great role in enhancing schools with school staff (Brown et al., 2002). They are also supposed to be mentors, strategists and managers as well as the representatives of the up-to-date regulations. Accordingly, there are various definitions to describe a supervisor. In its broad definition, supervision can be defined as the process of supervising and observing of authorities (Taymaz, 2011). Glickman (1990) describes supervision as the direct help to teachers, and schools function improving teaching by empowering curriculum, teachers and groups. Kapusuzoglu (2004) states that contemporary definitions of supervision underline the importance of service, cooperation, and democracy. Bursalioglu (2015) draws a framework like Glickman (1990), and defines it as a coordinated process of technical and social steps for common good. Lunenburg and Ornstein (2004) see supervision as a precaution against deterioration from the school functioning. According to Pierce and Rowell (2005), supervision is a developmental process, which is designed for teachers to gain success and skills, consciousness, autonomy and motivation. Overall, it is possible to say that a supervisor is a person who has a mastery over regulations, and observes and helps educational organizations function as expected.

As Cambridge English Dictionary (2016) suggests, change is to exchange one thing for another thing, especially of a similar type. Literally, change means getting something from a certain level to another level; replacing people or objects or getting personal knowledge, skills and gifts to a new level (Tasliyan and Karayilan, 2011). Celep (2000) looks from the improvement window and says that it is betterment of a mistake, or deterioration. Basaran (2004) describes change as follows: it is an observable difference in then and now of components of a whole. If one thinks that it is not a beginning, but a result they can agree with Celebioglu (1982) who thinks change happens at the end of the changes in environmental, societal, economic, politic and technological structures. Change happens when there is an unbalance between the restrictive and driving force (Lipit, 1969), which forces an organization or individuals to look for a change.

Liu and Bouguettaya (2016) suggest that there are two types of change: top-down changes and bottom-up changes. Top-down changes or mandated changes originate at government or bureaucratic level (cited in Clement, 2014). Bottom-up changes are the ones initiated by opponents of an organization. It is known that bottom-up changes take more time than top-down changes. When it comes to educational systems, it will not be wrong to say that most changes are still mandated or top-down way. As Hargreaves

(2004) suggests almost all educational changes are externally initiated. On the other hand, Fullan (1994) observes and states that a top- down model in educational changes is ineffective; and to Bailey (2000) this type of change is only helps teachers' marginalization. But, what do the changes make supervisors think? The answer to this question may be obsolete for most of them, as they are used to be equipped with another change in regulations every school term. As they are supposed to be the ones who know the laws and regulations thoroughly, what do these numerous changes make them feel toward change? These are the basic questions this study looks answers for.

Bringing a change to an organization successfully requires hard work. Lewin (1947) proposed a three steps model for a change project in any organization. The theory has three phases to manage the process as expected and planned as shown in Figure 1:

Figure 1

According to Lewin (1947), the first step in the changing process is to unfreeze the existing condition which involves preparing the organization to accept that a change is necessary. Unfreezing is important to overcome the strains of individual resistance and group conformity. In order to achieve unfreezing, increasing the driving forces that direct behaviour away from the status quo, and decreasing the restraining forces that negatively affect the movement from the existing balance will be useful. To break abulia and egotistical attitudes, it is sometimes necessary to bring about an emotional stir up. Robbins (2003) states that some activities can be used to prepare individuals for change such as motivating them, building trust and recognition for the need to change, and actively participating in recognizing problems and brainstorming solutions within a group. As Lewin (1947) prospects, this step may not be the same for all organizations, the unfreezing of the present level may involve quite different problems in different cases. Enlarging on Lewin's ideas, Schein (1996) suggests three phases necessary to achieve unfreezing: disconfirmation of the validity of the status quo, the induction of guilt or survival anxiety, and creating psychological safety. He argued that: "...unless sufficient psychological safety is created, the disconfirming information

will be denied or in other ways defended against, no survival anxiety will be felt, and consequently, no change will take place."

Lewin's second step is moving. In this step, it is necessary to move the target system to a new level of current situation. Three actions that can help in the action step include persuading individuals to agree that the status quo is not beneficial to them, and encouraging them to take in the problem from a new perspective, and work together for new, relevant information, and connecting the opinions of the group to well-respected. This is not an easy time as individuals as they are learning about the changes and need to be given time to understand and work with them. Support is crucial here and it can be in the form of training, coaching and expecting mistakes as part of the process. It may be helpful for individuals to allow them to develop their own solutions in this process. Here, groups and individuals move from a less acceptable to a more acceptable sets of behaviours (Schein, 1996). It must be noted that without reinforcement in this step, change could be short-lived (Lewin, 1947).

The third step of Lewin's three-step change model is refreezing. Refreezing seeks to stabilize the group at a new quasi-stationary equilibrium in order to ensure that the new behaviours are relatively safe from regression (Lewin, 1947). Individuals cannot be adapted if this step is not taken. It is the actual integration of the new values into the community values and traditions, policies and procedures (Robbins, 2003). New behaviour is the key here, as to some degree, it must be congruent with the rest of the behaviour, personality and environment of the learner or it will simply lead to a new round of disconfirmation (Schein, 1996). This is why Lewin says a successful change is a group activity. If the norms and policies are not transformed by the group members, change in individual behaviours will not sustain. Rather than individual, organizational change will also require change in policies or regulations as Cummings and Huse (1989) suggested.

Literature indicates that a high proportion of change initiatives are not successful (Beer ve Nohria, 2000). This may be because the reactions to change cannot be understood by the authorities. A large number of researches deal with how change recipients react and respond to change. Studies examining what employees actually do in terms of behaviour tend to focus on resistance to change (Guth and MacMillan, 1986). According to Piderit (2000), reactions to change include affective, cognitive and behavioural components. Researchers generally agree that employee resistance is one of the leading causes for the failure of change initiatives (Bovey and Hede, 2001; Waldersee and Griffiths, 1996). Individuals perceive change in different ways (Fullan, 1982). This may cause resistance among them. They can have a sense of uncertainty against change while working with the methods they are accustomed to. Also

individuals' misunderstanding of change can lead resistance (Conner and Lake, 1986). The problems caused by change in an organization include explicit-implicit, active-passive or direct or indirect resistance. These problems can be classified as alienation, conflict or crisis (Yeniçeri, 2002). Alienation is generally defined as the decrease in individuals' adaptation to the social, cultural and natural environment especially the decrease in control of their environment and this causes them loneliness and despair. Conflict can be caused by miscommunication between the parties or unsuccessful communication caused by misunderstanding about the changes that are put into practice or it can occur because of the severity of the change. If changes create much worse working conditions, rights and gains of employees, this may cause conflict. As a result of changing conditions, individuals feel like showing different roles, which causes role conflict. Change can also lead to crisis in the organization. Crisis is a significant and an urgent situation. It is the condition in which organization can find themselves in an unbalanced situation. Uncertainty, fast and sudden changes can cause a decrease in an organization's taking right decisions. If an organization doesn't take right decisions, a conflict can ensue (Yeniçeri, 2002).

Change is also one of the most crucial issues for educational organizations. During a change process in an educational organization, the head of the organization has a great responsibility in terms of making employees feel a part of change and manage the steps of change well. However, it is possible to observe that teachers or other personnel employed in state schools complain about the change's nature: being top-down and often. At the beginning of a school term, supervisors are informed about a newly changed regulation, teachers learn that they have got a new curriculum and course book, other personnel learn about new software to keep school data online. This atmosphere of 'total' change in every school term is far beyond reaching the expectations of change. This present study deals with supervisors' opinions about the changes regarding the supervision system and is believed to be a new perspective for the heads of the higher management who applies the changes without any attempt to 'unfreeze' the current situation. If one looks at the history of change in supervisory regulations in Turkish Education System, they could possibly recognize how radical and often they are. A chronicle of these changes is as follows:

Table 1: History of changes

- 1838 - A supervision system was founded in the Tanzimat Era to overcome teaching difficulties and improvement of teachers;
- 1846-47 - Teaching-learning process was handled by a ministry-like branch and supervisors were assigned to help teachers;

1857 - The Ministry of Education was founded;

1875 - Supervisors were to help teachers, there had to be a supervision chronicle at schools in which evaluation of teachers and management were to be noted, and these chronicles had to be kept by school principals;

1911 - Supervisors were to be selected among teachers employed in secondary or high education institutions, architects and doctors;

1923 - A regulation on supervision was released;

1925 - Culture supervision' was founded to explore and preserve the cultural heritage;

1927 - First regulation on the requirements for supervisor was released;

1938 - A law was put in force: supervisors were to be selected from Gazi Terbiye Enstitüsü graduates or any equivalent institutions abroad;

1940 - Supervisors were distributed to all regions;

1950 - Supervisors were called back to centers: Ankara, Istanbul and Izmir;

1958 - Elementary school teachers were trained to be supervisors to meet the shortage;

1962 - Supervisors' job description included guiding, improving, helping teachers; making research on school development, material selection and school buildings;

1970 - The head of supervision department was to be an ordinary member of Ministry of Education Council;

1999 - 5 years of teaching requirement was changed to 8 years of teaching experience to become a supervisor;

Today – Though the law remains same, following changes were made through regulations:

- Regionally and centrally employed supervisors were accepted as the same;
- They were to work under the head of supervision in city centers;
- Ministry (central) supervisors were to complete compulsory service when they were sent to regions;
- Their teaching experience were to cover their compulsory service years;
- Supervisors could work in the same city no more than 8 years;
- Under the head of a supervision department, no more than 100 supervisors could be employed;
- To be assigned as a vice supervisor, one must be a graduate of faculty of education, letter, law, political sciences, finance and business, economy, business or religious studies;
- Ones who have 8 years of teaching experience would not need to take KPSS;
- One must be no more than 35 years old to be a vice supervisor (formerly 40);
- Appointment of the heads for the department will be done by the Minister and advisors, there will be no requirement for the position;

- Supervisors cannot ask for a change due to career/learning circumstances

As clearly stated, the supervisors are always facing a new regulation, reactions to which are thought to affect their job, motivation and performance. The answers to the following questions are sought in this study:

1. What do supervisors feel about the most recent change in the regulation?
2. Do they feel as a part of changes? What do they think about timing/necessity of the change?
3. Why do the changes happen so often? Is it top-down or bottom up way?
4. What are the problems or achievements of the changes for Turkish education system?

2. Material and Methods

2.1 The Model of the Study

This research aims to find out the supervisors' reactions towards change. Qualitative data collection techniques were used to gather information. Qualitative technique was preferred for systematic examination of meanings revealed as a result of experiences of people who are subjects of the research (Ekiz, 2003). Qualitative studies are rather more interested in process than products or outcomes. Hence, meanings are more important in qualitative studies (Merriam, 1988). Semi-structured interviews were mostly preferred in qualitative studies due to their certain level of standardized yet flexible structure, since they overcome limitations of surveys and tests requiring filled-in or written answers, and they help to obtain in-depth information (Yıldırım & Şimşek, 2011). Semi-structured interview form was used to collect data, and seven questions were posed to participants. Obtained responses were analyzed via descriptive analysis methods, and the results presented in data tables.

2.2 Population and Sample

The sampling of the study covers 11/19 of the supervisors employed in Giresun. Some of the supervisors were out of town for training or personal reasons; all the remaining supervisors volunteered for sharing their opinions on changes.

2.3 Data Collection Tool

As a data collection tool, seven questions were written down following the steps: First the theories regarding change were studied by two researchers, and Lewin's theory of change was accepted to be best explaining the nature of change. Each steps of change unfreeze; change and refreeze were read and observed in different examples, mostly

workplaces. Second, theory based steps and requirements led to writing semi-structured questions. In order to increase the internal reliability of the analyses, the questions written by the researchers were reviewed by two independent researchers, and their opinions regarding whether each theme was appropriately associated or not. In addition, the questions were piloted, based on the comments; the received feedback was followed to finalize the questions.

This study was conducted with active, personal participation of the researcher. The data collection tool was personally handed to the supervisors, who were visited by pre-arranged appointment. The researcher explained the importance of receiving sincere and accurate responses to the questions, and then the supervisors were informed that they could respond to the questions in writing or face-to-face recording. All of the supervisors stated that they could answer the semi-structured interview forms in writing. The written forms were reviewed in the presence of the supervisors and ambiguous points were clarified by additional questioning.

For reliability of the question forms, the questions were verified by an educational scientist and themes were analyzed by him. Miles and Huberman (1984) argued that at least 70% agreement was required to ascertain reliability during the analysis process. The related formula:

$$\text{Reliability} = \frac{\text{Number of Agreements}}{\text{Total Number of Agreements} + \text{Total of Disagreements}}$$

The results for the interviews were 87% agreements, which were above the acceptable levels mentioned earlier.

3. Results and Discussion

In this study, data was analyzed through descriptive analysis method. Representative quotations were also selected in order to enable readers to be able to see that a range of participants has contributed to the data (Anderson, 2010). Descriptive analysis is a technique used to summarize and interpret the obtained data based on predetermined themes, where direct quotations are used to reveal participants' views in an attractive manner, and to interpret obtained findings in a cause-and-effect relationship framework (Yıldırım & Şimşek, 2011).

The results of this present study were organized under research questions. In order to find out what supervisors feel about the most recent change in the regulation they were asked about the preparations before applying a change to make them get

ready for it. Almost all the participants agree that their opinions are not valued by higher management. The opinions of the supervisors are indicated in Table 2:

Table 2: Preparations Made Before the Change Applied

All the changes are made fait accompli. No one worries about preparing us for a change (P2).
Changes are done in the center, and we hear the rumors and say that 'no way' 'this is impossible' but we learn that they have already done it. We aren't surprised any more, it is like learned helplessness. They are more intelligent than us, there is no need to prepare us, we are always ready (P8)

The participants are, then, asked to answer the following question: *“What kind of supports do you get for getting acquainted with the new regulation?”*. The responses are organized under two titles. Table 3 shows the titles.

Table 3: Support to Prepare for a Change

Support to Prepare for a Change	f
There is no effort to prepare us for the change (P1), (P2), (P7) , (P8)	4
In-service training & informative legal documents (P3), (P4), (P5), (P6),(P9), (P10), (P11)	7

As seen above, while some of the participants seem to feel any support from the Ministry and the higher management board, some of them think that there is enough support to make them prepared for the upcoming change. 36% of the participants support the idea that their opinions or readiness is not cared by the Ministry. For example, participant 2 says that *“for the last ten years or more, we, supervisors have had no trust in the Ministry due to the policies they have made. This makes us always ready for a good or a bad change (P2)”*. On the other hand, majority of the participants (%63) are for the idea that there have been efforts to make them ready for the changes. *“Informative legal documents and in-service training are presented to make us feel ready (P3)”*. Another participant added seminars and briefings to the current efforts.

A third question was asked to the participants to find out the direction of the changes; whether they are top-down (mandated) or bottom-up way. The question is: *“To what extent you agree that changes are top-down in the organization?”*. A great number of the participants agree on the fact that the change in the organization and in the country is made top-down way. The Table 4 shows the directions of change made in the organization.

Table 4: Direction of Change

Direction of Change	f
The changes are top-down (mandated) (P2), (P3), (P4) , (P6), (P7), (P9), (P10), (P11)	8
The changes are bottom-up way (P8)	1
Changes should be bottom-up (P1),(P5)	2

When asked about the direction of changes in the organization, 72% of the participants say that they are top-down way. They underline the importance of problems, experiences, observations during the practice, and inclusion of the reasons gathered through the field experience. Participant 11 states that *“changes are made from the top management; I completely agree with that. The regulations do not cover the problems we face in the field, so we always feel the necessity to ask for details, which delays the solution (P11).”* Only one of the participants favors the idea that changes are not always made top-down way, s/he states that *“I don’t think it is always top-down way, sometimes it may cause problems and require to be taken back, which causes bigger problems (P8).”* 18% of the participants did not give a direct answer to the question; rather they prefer to give general information about how changes should be made. For example, *“Adopting a top-down style in changes is not a good approach; the practitioners need to consider the problems faced, instead (P5).”*

Another research question was asked to the participants to answer: *“What are your opinions on the reasons of the changes applied?”.* According to the supervisors’ opinions, it is seen that the reasons of the changes applied vary. The reasons given by the participants are shown in Table 5.

Table 5: Reasons for the Change

Reasons for the change	f
Central supervising (P3, P4, P6, P8)	4
Reorganization (P10, P3)	2
Improving the supervision (P5, P9)	2
The management change (P11)	1
Personal greed (P1)	1
No reason (P7)	1

As shown in Table 5 four participants emphasized that the need for *“central supervising”* is the main reason of the changes applied. One participant stated, *“I think these changes result from the decision which is aimed at centralizing the supervision (P4)”*. Two of the participants think that one of the reasons can be *“reorganization”*. One participant said, *“These changes are based on the reorganization concern. In the period of management change, government needs to change their management perspective, reorganize their system and*

centralize their control (P10)". Another reason stated by the participants the Ministry applied the changes because they want to improve the supervision. One participant said *"It's found out by the Ministry that the previous system couldn't work efficiently (P5)"*. *"Personal greed"* was stated as a reason for the current change. One participant expressed *"I don't think politicians has no idea about the change. This can only be explained with politicians' personal greed (P1)"*.

Supervisors were then asked: *"What possible problems do you think you might have about the new regulation?"*. The opinions of the supervisors are grouped under two titles; *the possible problems the supervisors can have* and *the possible problems the supervision system can have*. From some of the supervisors' perspective, the effect and success of supervision will decrease and the role of supervision will be perceived as unnecessary with the new regulation. One example statement given by the participant is: *"The supervision will be found unnecessary by teachers and principals (P2)"*. Another participant stated *"The supervision will not be made in the organizations and because of the lack of supervision; the success of the organizations will happen by chance (P1)"*.

The opinions of the supervisors show that they can have a plenty of problems with the new regulation. These problems can be listed as in Table 6.

Table 6: Problems that the supervisor can have

Problems that supervisors can have	f
Work load (P1), (P3), (P7), (P11)	4
Lack of motivation (P9),(P12)	2
No problem (P5), (P6)	2
Change of job definition (P4)	1
Conflict (P8)	1
Work load (P1), (P3), (P7), (P11)	1

The following statements are quotations from the interview with the supervisors. The term *"work load"* was expressed by four participants. One stated *"Unless the new supervisor team does not complete their job, the supervisors in the national education directorate will try to do their job restricted by the new regulation (P7)"*. Another participant stated *"It is not possible to carry on the job of supervision, inspection and education with 500 supervisors. Besides, restricting our scope and not making necessary regulations about our rights have affected our motivation in a negative way (P11)." Another statement expressed by participants is "lack of motivation". Before any change is not applied, one may think it will produce efficient results soon. But one participant stated "It is impossible to implement the change in a short period of time because both the new team and already existing ones are not motivated enough (P2)"*.

Another research question was to identify the opinions of the supervisors on the gains of the new regulation when it becomes successful. The analysis of the responses indicates that most of the supervisors expressed a negative opinion. Only two of them gave a positive opinion. The negative opinions obtained from the responses of the supervisors and example quotations are given below:

Table 7: Opinions on gains of new regulation

Opinions on <i>gains of new regulation</i>	<i>f</i>
Negative opinion (P1), (P2), (P3), (P4), (P6), (P8), (P9), (P11)	8
Positive opinion (P5), (P10)	2
Neutral (P7)	1

Analysis of the responses concerning the gains of new regulation if it is successful point out that most of the participants reported negative opinions. According to the these, it can be said that success is not expected by the higher management because the new regulation hasn't been well-organized. The following statements exemplify some of negative opinions given by participants.

"It is going to happen by chance if the new regulation becomes successful. It isn't expected for the supervisors, who are chosen by the interview, to do their job fairly as well as cutting down the number of the supervisors (P1)".

"I don't think the new regulation will contribute to our education system. With the new practice, schools will be supervised every ten years, which used to supervise every three years before, and the new supervision perspective will practice just as a matter of formality (P2)."

"I think that the new regulation will not become successful owing to the impossibility of supervising 95,000 schools with 500 supervisors (P3)."

The following example quotations show that some supervisors express a positive opinion.

"With the help of the new regulation, the supervision system will gain power, become more efficient and effective as well as having a more objective and independent function (P5)".

"Inspection and supervision will be conducted by the control of the Ministry so this is going to provide a more objective perspective on the supervision. Problems can be solved more quickly and so the defects of the system will be improved in a short time (P10)."

The statements of the supervisors given above indicate that the supervisors worry about the possible problems caused by the new regulation. If this new practice cannot be managed well, the supervision will lose its effectiveness according to the opinions of the supervisors. On the other hand, their expressions frequently focus on the number of the supervisors in the new regulation.

The last question was to identify the losses of the Turkish Education system if the new regulation becomes unsuccessful. All of the supervisors are nearly certain that The Turkish Education System is going to have some major problems. Table... shows the losses of the system.

Table 8: Losses of the system

Losses of the System	f
Loss of time (P1), (P2), (P6), (P7), (P9), (P10)	6
Ineffective supervision (P3), (P4), (P5), (P11)	4
Loss of trust (P8)	1

Most of the participants define their opinions in terms of the loss of time which might show its effects in the long run. Examples of statements containing the term “*the loss of time*” are given as follows: “*If the new regulation fails to achieve its goals, another kind of change will be applied and this will cause to waste time and effort (P6)*”. One participant stated “*As we have experienced a lot in recent years, new regulations and changes about supervision, endless new search and loss of time is inevitable (P2)*”. Another term stated by the participants is “*ineffective supervision*”. One participant stated “*The job of supervision will be ineffective because of insufficient number of supervisors while more schools to be supervised and the variety of problems the Ministry must handle with (P3)*”. One said “*The efficiency and performance of supervision will decrease, on the other hand; the power of the management in the province will increase on supervision (P5)*”.

It can be said that these statements indicate the new regulation will bring new problems. The system might enter a period in which both the people giving service and those getting service have some difficulties.

Educational organizations, which were founded to meet the educational needs of the society, have been under the pressure of a continuous change and innovation for the last fifty years (Fullan, 2001; Hargreaves, 2002; Wallace, 2004). In this respect, this present study offers a different point of view in this research area. Even though it has some limitations, this research has provided some considerable results regarding the process of the changes which were applied in an educational organization and has given valuable results about how the changes were managed. The findings of the study revealed that most of the supervisors, who can be called as direct practitioners of

changes, were not prepared for the changes by the higher management before the changes were applied. The statements indicate that they were just asked their opinions about the changes after they had already been planned. In fact, according to Lewin (1947) the first step during the process of changes is to prepare the organization to accept the change before applied. He stated that this step is necessary in terms of overcoming the strains of individual resistance and group conformity. In this respect, the higher management did not make their organization prepared for the changes. Regardless of the things aiming organizational change or the content of the planned changes, the most important issue to remember is that man has the leading role in all such changes (Lawler and Worley, 2006). According to Susanto (2008) some factors such as employees' behaviors, competences, knowledge on change, motivation affect the success of the change. In this study, most of the participants expressed they lost their motivation as a result of lack of information given by the higher management.

4. Recommendations

In the light of the findings, supervisors think that they are not a part of planning of a change process, though they are expected to be the first to comprehend and comply with them. Therefore, it may be an improvement for the MoNE authorities to prepare briefings, surveys or interviews about the practices and to analyze the needs for a change. In the practice step of the change, it can be recommended to take each step in coordination with the supervisors working in the field. If their feedbacks are provided and evaluated during the practice, the solutions to the existing problems will not delay. As a third step, change needs refreezing, which requires understanding and accepting. Accepting can be in different forms: either one can accept and apply by agreeing or one can apply the changes without agreeing, taking them just as another legal liability. As the latter one is not what change managers have had in mind, it is going to be a time consuming and coordinated work to involve all the parties from beginning to end. For further studies, it is recommended to conduct the same kind of research in different cities or countries where more supervisors can participate. This may enlarge the perspective from which MoNE looks before starting to apply a change in the procedures.

5. Conclusion

The study pointed out how changes are applied by the higher management from supervisors' views. The findings show that the higher management applies the changes,

and then they inform the supervisors. However, the literature tells that efforts for change should be continued through teamwork and cooperation (Duren, 2000). In terms of cooperation and teamwork, this kind of applying a change leads uncertainty among the supervisors because they state that they were not prepared; they are expected to be prepared themselves for the new practices.

The statements also indicate that the higher management tries to inform the supervisors about the changes through some legal documents and sometimes organize seminars or in-service trainings to make them adopt the applied regulations. But it is seen that they are not frequent enough to make them understand the changes and its practices adequately. When they are asked about why the changes were applied, their responses indicated that they had positive and negative opinions about the reasons of the changes. According to the literature, their responses can be categorized in two titles; internal reasons and external reasons. Öztop (2014) says that changes in economic conditions, technological developments, market changes, legal amendments, and changing customer preferences due to social and political changes are considered among the external reasons of organizational change, whereas human resources problems, organizational inadequacies, financial problems, managerial behaviors and decisions as well as in-house innovation are considered among the internal reasons for a change. In this study central supervising, reorganization, personal greed and improving the act of supervising were exemplified for the reasons of the changes. Accordingly, the changes were applied because of the internal reasons in this organization.

Employees' reactions to change are influenced by a number of factors. It is reasonable to expect employees to react since the process of change involves going from the known to the unknown, and when employees react, it is important to distinguish between the symptoms of their reactions and the causes behind them (Bovey & Hede, 2001). When the participants are asked in order to reveal the possible problems that the new supervisors group and the interviewers are going to have, their responses show that they think negatively. From the participants' point of view, the inefficiency of the supervision due to the new system will cause failure in the organization. It is also pointed out that the participants believe the supervision will be perceived as an unnecessary and useless for teachers or principals so this will result in lack of motivation among the supervisors. If any organization wants a long term change, they should be sure about the employees' opinions on the new process they will find themselves. In this study, the findings revealed the participants do not believe the change will be successful.

The success of organizational change initiatives lies in the reaction of employees; it is crucial to communicate to employees' information about the change to positively influence their reactions. Yet, when the responses of the participants were analyzed, it was seen they were negative towards the new regulation. Communication managed poorly during change process can result in resistance and exaggerating negative aspects of the change. Effective communication reduces employees' uncertainty, and a negative correlation exists between uncertainty and employees' willingness to accept change (Elving, 2005). So it can be concluded the participants are having difficulty in accepting the change and its possible results.

In general, it is possible to speak of two types of change: planned and unplanned. "Planned change" is desirable for organizations, and means a change realized with the participation of and support of the members of an organization. "Unplanned change," on the other hand, is defined as inevitable change undergone by organizations, consciously or not, due to unexpected circumstances (Escalente, 2005; Özdemir, 2000). The study revealed that the Turkish education system has some gains if the changes are successful and there will be some losses if they are not successful as a result of the new supervision regulation applied. But the findings indicated losses would be more than gains. In terms of gains, the act of supervision will be more effective and objective with the new regulation according to the participants' point of view. While, the possible examples of losses given by the participants show that the changes will affect the Turkish education system, negatively. The reason why the participants thought like this is because the changes are not planned. As Özmen & Sönmez (2007) states planning the change and ensuring its sustainability through successfully managing and implementing it is crucial for an organization to improve itself, to respond to demands, and to successfully continue to exist for a longer time. From this point of view, this new regulation is thought not to give the expected results.

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